

Multifunctional Structure-plus-Power Composites

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SUMMARY: Composite materials with structure-plus-power multifunctionality are being developed for unmanned-air-vehicles (UAV) in order to extend their flight endurance time. Three types of structure-power materials are under consideration: structure-battery for micro-air-vehicle components, autophagous (self-consuming) structure-fuel for providing mechanical stiffness and strength prior to being transformed into propulsion energy, and variform structure-fuel, which uses gaseous or liquid fuel as structure and actuation media for morphing UAV's. We describe a new framework for designing multifunctional materials consisting of performance indices and analysis methods. The framework is applied to two multifunctional material systems under development.

KEYWORDS: Multifunctional, structure-battery, autophagous, variform, composite design

INTRODUCTION

Multifunctional materials are developed to achieve overall system-level performance enhancement through the reduction of redundancy between subsystem materials and functions. A measure of efficacy for multifunctionality is given by the difference in system performance between the multifunctional and the baseline "unifunctional" designs. This requires physical prototypes that can be tested or robust performance models for each design.

The question of which materials and functions to join is best answered by considering the targeted system performance index expressed in terms of various sub-system design parameters. The feasibility of a multifunctional design depends on the internal and external interfacing capabilities and physical compatibility of the desired combination of sub-system functions. Multifunctionality can be more effectively implemented at the start of a system design process due to the greater flexibility in selecting and integrating sub-system materials and functions.

The combination of structure and battery in the design of an electric-propelled unmanned air vehicle (UAV) is a good example of how materials/functions are identified for possible integration as a multifunctional material system. For UAV's, the system metric is flight endurance time, which is explicitly related to the available battery energy, subsystem weights, and aerodynamic parameters [1]:

$$\text{Flight Endurance Time } t_E = \left(\frac{\text{Total Available Battery Energy } E_B \eta_B}{\text{Sub-System Weights } (W_S + W_B + W_{PR} + W_{PL})^{3/2}} \right) \times \left[\frac{\text{Propeller Efficiency } \rho S C_L^3}{2 C_D^2} \right]^{1/2} \eta_P \quad (1)$$

Aerodynamics,
Geometry

Equation (1) shows that combining battery with one of the other sub-systems may provide a viable route for increasing available energy or decreasing total weight. That is, we want to look for material/function combinations involving the battery (B) and the structure (S), propulsion (PR), or payload (PL) sub-systems. Consideration of the individual weight fractions of the various sub-systems shows that the structure and battery each contribute 20-40% to the total UAV weight [1]. This implies that these two sub-systems have probably the best potential for increasing UAV performance via multifunctionality.

The normalized change in endurance with changes in energy or structure and battery weight is:

$$\frac{\Delta t_E}{t_E} = \frac{\Delta(E_B \eta_B)}{E_B \eta_B} - \frac{3}{2} \frac{(\Delta W_S + \Delta W_B)}{W_{total}} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) shows that lowering weight is one-and-a-half times more effective in increasing endurance than increasing the battery energy. Introducing multifunctional structure-battery into a design increases the available energy, decreases the structure weight and possibly battery weight, and adds structure-battery weight. The actual gain in enhancement depends on the exact details of the multifunctional implementation. In many cases, the mechanical and energy-storage properties of a multifunctional material may not be as good as the individual property values achieved by “optimized” unifunctional materials. The best way to maximize gains from multifunctionality is to target mechanically underutilized structure for replacement by multifunctional structure-power material.

Three multifunctional structure-power concepts are being investigated for application to UAV systems. The first involves *structure-battery* materials for electric-powered UAV’s. A thin laminate plastic-lithium-ion (PLI) bicell material is being combined with structure enhancing materials and packaging to achieve multifunctional performance. In battery systems, the amount of energy that can be stored and delivered depends on the nature of the anode and cathode materials used in the cell, which determines the voltage, and the amount of active materials present, which determines the Ah capacity. Only a fraction of the theoretical energy storage capacity is realized in practice. The essence of a battery cell is the cathode-electrolyte/separator-anode. Actual battery cells also require current collectors that are good conductors, cell packaging, and terminal electrodes. These latter “materials of construction” add non-energy-storing weight and volume to the battery thereby decreasing the apparent performance. The same is true of the structural additive materials in the structure-battery implementation. The exact nature and amount of these structural additive and construction materials depends on the mechanical and electrical operational requirements, battery chemistry, overall geometry, and operating environment. Selection and arrangement of the constituent materials and integration as UAV structure are the primary technical challenges associated with this concept.

The second concept, *autophagous structure-fuel*, focuses on the exploitation of structural materials that are capable of being used for propulsion energy, either directly or indirectly via chemical transformation. The structure-fuel material provides enhancement to the strength and stiffness during high or peak loading, prior to utilization for propulsion energy via combustion or chemical conversion. Hydrogen generating materials (e.g., metal-borohydrides) and combustible polymers are being considered for their structure-power potential. The primary technical challenge is identifying appropriate structure-fuel materials coupled with light-weight, efficient material-to-energy transformation schemes.

The third concept, *variform structure-power*, involves morphing aircraft structures whose geometry and mechanical characteristics directly and controllably link with the propulsion fuel. The idea is to use pressurized gaseous or liquid fuel to equilibrate large-deformations of an elastic structure. Gano & Renaud [2] have performed an analysis that predicts a 22% increase in range or endurance is possible for an UAV powered by internal combustion engine with airfoils that morph from NACA 23015 to FX 60-126 during flight. Developing robust, durable UAV structures that are capable of morphing in a useful manner is the principal technical challenge associated with variform structure-power.

The focus of this paper is on design methods for multifunctional structure-power materials. We begin with a description of performance indices for multifunctional performance of composites and a computational tool for parametric analysis of composite structure-power materials. These methods/tools are then demonstrated in two design configuration studies for a structure-battery laminate and an autophagous strut. Discussion of the results and their relevance to multifunctional design follows.

METHOD

The “Materials Selection” approach, developed by Ashby [3,5] is useful for ranking the performance of material with respect to system-level objectives. Modifications are needed for composite materials, however, because the performance depends on both the material and the constituent architecture or geometry and arrangement within the cross-section (e.g., see [5]).

Mechanical Performance

Consideration is limited here to prismatic composite members. Constituent materials and cross-section geometry is constant along the length of the member, which is taken as the x-axis. Modulus-weighted cross-sectional parameters are employed to simplify the mechanical analysis by allowing the direct use of standard ‘‘Mechanics of Materials’’ equations. Related details can be found in Thomas & Qidwai [6] or Allen & Haisler [7].

Four internal loads are possible in the planar problem. They are assumed to pass-through the modulus-weighted centroid, defined below, and are represented in Figure 1 by:

$$\vec{R} = P\hat{x} + V_y\hat{y} \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{M} = T\hat{x} + M_{xz}\hat{z} \quad (3)$$

P is the axial force; V_y is the transverse shear force; M_{xz} is the bending moment, and T is the torque.

The origin and orientation of the $\hat{y}'\text{-}\hat{z}'$ coordinate axes for the cross-section are arbitrary (see, for example, Figure 2). The $\hat{y}\text{-}\hat{z}$ axes are located at the modulus-weighted (MW) centroid with the same orientation as the $\hat{y}'\text{-}\hat{z}'$ axes. They define the operative coordinate system from which all points in the cross-section are referenced. Modulus weighted parameters (defined below) are denoted with a ‘‘*’’ superscript.

Area:
$$A^* := \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E_i}{E_R} A_i \quad (4)$$

Centroid Location:
$$\bar{y}'^* := \frac{1}{A^*} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E_i}{E_R} A_i \bar{y}'_i, \quad \bar{z}'^* := \frac{1}{A^*} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E_i}{E_R} A_i \bar{z}'_i \quad (5)$$

2nd Moment of Inertia of Area:
$$I_{zz}^* := \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E_i}{E_R} \left\{ (I_{zz0})_i + \bar{y}'_i{}^2 A_i \right\}, \quad I_{yz}^* := 0 \text{ (symmetric)} \quad (6)$$

Polar Moment of Inertia (Circular Annular Composites):
$$K^* := \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{G_i}{G_R} (K_0)_i \quad (7)$$

In the above expressions, n is the total number of constituents; E_i and G_i are the tensile and shear moduli for the i^{th} constituent; E_R and G_R are arbitrary reference moduli; \bar{y}'^* and \bar{z}'^* are the MW centroid location relative to the $\hat{y}'\text{-}\hat{z}'$ system; \bar{y}'_i and \bar{z}'_i are the i^{th} material centroid location in the $\hat{y}'\text{-}\hat{z}'$ system; \bar{y}_i and \bar{z}_i are the i^{th} material centroid location in the $\hat{y}\text{-}\hat{z}$ system; $(I_{zz0})_i$ is the 2nd areal moment for the i^{th} constituent about its centroidal axes; and $(K_0)_i$ is the ‘‘effective’’ polar moment of inertia of the i^{th} constituent about its centroidal axes.

We have defined a new set of performance indices for composites, listed in Table 1, which we denote as **material-architecture indices**. They utilize **composite shape factors**, shown in Table 2, to account for the interaction between composition, geometry and arrangement on mechanical performance. Composite shape factors are identical in form to their homogeneous counterparts [3,4], but with the cross-section parameters replaced by modulus-weighted quantities. The material-architecture indices are identical in form to material performance indices with shape factors, and can be used to rank and optimize composite configurations (i.e., constituent materials and cross-section architecture) for minimum weight under a variety of loading and constraint conditions. Using this new composites performance methodology, system mass is related to the material-architecture index, $f(M \cup A)$, as shown:

$$m = \rho AL = \text{Constant} \times \left[f(M \cup A) \right]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

In Table 1, E_R and G_R are the reference moduli; $(\sigma_0)_i$ and $(\tau_0)_i$ are the tensile and torsional failure stresses for the i^{th} constituent; ρ is the composite mass density, defined by:

$$\rho := \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{A_i}{A} \rho_i \quad \text{and} \quad A := \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \quad (9)$$

where ρ_i and A_i are the i^{th} constituent's density and area, and $\phi_{A,B,T}^{*e}$ and $(\phi_{A,B,T}^{*f})_i$ are the composite shape factors for stiffness and strength (Table 2) defined as:

$$\phi_{A,B,T}^{*e} = \frac{S_{A,B,T}^*}{S_0} \quad \text{and} \quad (\phi_{A,B,T}^{*f})_i = \frac{(\text{FailLoad}_{A,B,T}^*)_i}{(\text{FailLoad})_0} \quad (10)$$

Composite component type, specified and free variables	Deflection-limited design	Load-limited design
Tie (tensile or compressive axial load) Axial force, length, and stiffness or strength specified; total cross-section area free	$\frac{E_R \phi_A^{*e}}{\rho}$	$\min_i \left\{ \frac{(\phi_A^{*f})_i (\sigma_0)_i}{\rho} \right\}$
Beam (bending-moment load) Bending moment, length, and stiffness or strength specified; total cross-section area free	$\frac{[E_R \phi_B^{*e}]^{1/2}}{\rho}$	$\min_i \left\{ \frac{[(\phi_B^{*f})_i (\sigma_0)_i]^{2/3}}{\rho} \right\}$
Torsion Bar or Tube (torque load) Torque, length, and stiffness or strength specified; total cross-section area free	$\frac{[G_R \phi_T^{*e}]^{1/2}}{\rho}$	$\min_i \left\{ \frac{[(\phi_T^{*f})_i (\tau_0)_i]^{2/3}}{\rho} \right\}$
Column (compressive axial load) Axial force, length, stiffness or strength, and boundary connections specified; total cross-section area free	$\frac{[E_R \phi_B^{*e}]^{1/2}}{\rho}$	$\min_i \left\{ \frac{(\phi_A^{*f})_i (\sigma_0)_i}{\rho} \right\}$

Table 1: Material-architecture performance indices for light-weight composite components with deflection or load limitations. Load-limited designs are controlled by the initial failure of one of the constituents.

Design Constraint	Mode of Loading		
	Axial	Bending	Torsion
Stiffness	$\phi_A^{*e} = \frac{A^*}{A}$	$\phi_B^{*e} = \frac{4\pi I_{zz}^*}{A^2}$	$\phi_T^{*e} = \frac{2\pi K^*}{A^2}$
Strength	$(\phi_A^{*f})_i = \frac{E_R}{E_i} \frac{A^*}{A}$	$(\phi_B^{*f})_i = \frac{4\sqrt{\pi}}{A^{3/2}} \frac{E_R}{E_i} \frac{I_{zz}^*}{(y_{max})_i}$	$(\phi_T^{*f})_i = \frac{2\sqrt{\pi}}{A^{3/2}} \frac{G_R}{G_i} \frac{K^*}{(r_{max})_i}$

Table 2: Composite shape factors used with the material-architecture performance indices.

$S_{A,B,T}^*$ is the axial (A), bending (B), or torsional (T) stiffness of the shaped-composite component, and S_0 is the stiffness of a similarly loaded homogeneous, circular shaped component with the same total cross-sectional area and moduli values E_R and G_R . $(\text{FailLoad}_{A,B,T}^*)_i$ is the failure load (axial, bending,

or torque) for the i^{th} component of the shaped-composite, and $(FailLoad)_0$ is the failure load for an identically loaded circular component that is homogeneous with the same total cross-sectional area and strength as the i^{th} constituent and modulus values E_R and G_R . Composite shape factors are used in this work to connect the “free” material-architecture design variables with the constraint equation(s).

Electrical Performance

Several factors play a role in the process of storing and retrieving energy from an energy-storage system. An important performance characteristic is the amount of energy that can be recovered from the system for a given power draw rate. For batteries and other electrical energy storage devices, this is typically manifested in curves of specific energy, e (energy per unit weight), or energy density, E (energy per unit volume), versus specific power, p (power per unit weight) or power density, P (power per unit volume). Plots of specific energy versus specific power are referred in the literature as Ragone plots [8]. Figure 3 shows approximate Ragone data for capacitors, batteries, and fuel cells [9]. Capacitors hold less energy than batteries or fuel cells but are capable of discharging it much more quickly. This is because energy storage in capacitors involves the stretching of bonds to create electrical dipoles whereas energy storage in batteries and fuel cells occurs via ion transport and the making and breaking of chemical bonds. Each particular energy storage material and device will have a unique energy-power curve, and this curve may be influenced by other factors like temperature, in the case of battery cells. Other energy storage media like combustibles or a mechanical flywheel are commonly characterized by one or a few energy-power points, not an energy-power curve.

Computational Design Tools

A set of computational design tools has been developed for analyzing the mechanical-energy-storage performance capabilities of structure-power components with: a) circular-annular, b) rectangular-annular, c) arbitrary-box and d) multi-layered cross-section configurations. The Structure-Battery Design Tool (SBDT), as it is called, is implemented in Excel spreadsheet form [6] and can be used for performing parametric design studies. The independent parameters are constituent material properties and geometric quantities related to constituent size and placement within the cross-section (i.e., architecture). Computed quantities include: mechanical stiffness and failure loads for axial, bending, torsion, shear, and buckle loading; volumetric and lineal weight densities; and several mass and volume normalized energy and power storage capacity measures. The mechanical behavior is modeled using standard mechanics of materials formulations with modulus weighted cross-section properties. The first page, denoted as “Input-Output”, performs calculations on a single design. The second page, denoted “Parametric”, has the same entries from the “Input-Output” page arranged along a single row for parametric design studies.

Structure-Battery Laminate

The structure-battery laminates are comprised of polymer-lithium-ion (PLI) bicell layers with a barrier layer packaging and with and without mechanical reinforcements. The PLI bicell (Figure 4) stores and delivers electrical energy via “rocking-chair” transport of lithium ions between the anode and cathode layers [8,10,11]. The anode and cathode particles are held together in layer form by a PVDF+HFP polymer matrix (~10% of the total dry bicell weight) that bonds with the separator layer. The PVDF+HFP matrix effectively “glues” the various cell layers together [10]. Expanded metal meshes are embedded in the active layers for current collection, and these active layers are laminated together with microporous, PVDF+HFP coated polyolefin layers as separators [11]. The electrolyte is highly hygroscopic, and the bicell must be protected with barrier-layer packaging. The chosen packaging uses polypropylene as a heat-seal layer on the inside, aluminum foil as a moisture barrier-layer, and biaxial nylon as a tough moldable layer on the outside (Figure 5).

Two configurations with mechanical reinforcements are considered. The first uses woven carbon fiber (five-harness satin weave; Thornel T-300 fibers; 1K tows; 24x24 tows/inch) just inside of the packaging. The second uses a carbon-epoxy layer (Hercules A280-5H) outside of the packaging.

Configurations with one, four, or eight layers of PLI plus packaging, with or without reinforcement are considered (Figure 6). The constituent properties are listed in Table 3. The Structure-Battery Design Tool is used to calculate the material-architecture and energy performance indices for a variety of configurations. Figure 7 plots performance as a function of number of bicell layers (1,4, and 8) for plain packaged and minimally reinforced (0.20 mm thick carbon weave and 0.254 mm thick carbon-epoxy) configurations. Figure 8 plots performance as a function of the reinforcement thickness for the 8-bicell layer configuration.

Material	Modulus, E (GPa)	Strength σ_0 (MPa)	Density ρ (g/cm ³)	Thickness t (cm)
Telcordia Plastic-Lithium-Ion Bicell	1.02	3.90	2.540	0.054
Dai-Nippon EP-40 Packaging	4.60	16.8	1.290	0.01
T-300 Carbon 5-Harness Satin Weave (1k tows)	36.5	548	0.560	0.0220
Hercules A280-5H Carbon-Epoxy Prepreg	72.4	690	1.1	0.0254

Table 3: Constituent properties for the structure-battery laminates.

Autophagous Struts

Autophagous structure-fuel materials are being explored for possible use in extending UAV endurance time. One particular design investigated is an autophagous strut with a 2.5 cm outer diameter tube of aluminum, titanium, or carbon-epoxy composite and an inner-tube of structure-fuel material (Figure 9). Magnesium-iron supercorroding alloy or carbon-polymer composite are considered in this example as possible structure-fuel materials. The Mg-Fe alloy dissolves quickly when exposed to an electrolyte, generating 9.9 kJ/g of energy (electrolyte weight included) in the form of heat (55%) and hydrogen gas (45%). The polymer composite generates 16 kJ/g of thermal energy via combustion. The hydrogen can be used with a fuel cell to generate electrical power or the hydrogen and the polymer composite can be burned and used with thermoelectric elements to generate electrical power. The Structure-Battery Design Tool (modified for appropriate energy calculations) is used to calculate the axial material-architecture index for stiffness and specific energy. Mechanical properties for the constituents are given in Table 4 and results of the analysis are shown in Figure 10.

Structure Materials	Density ρ (g/cm ³)	Modulus E (GPa)	Strength σ_0 (MPa)
7075-T6 Aluminum	2.81	72	505
Ti-6Al-4V Titanium	4.43	114	1100
Carbon-Epoxy	1.50	190	810
Structure-Fuel Materials			
Mg-5%Fe Supercorroding Alloy	1.81	44	90
PSI Polymer with 30% Chopped Carbon Fiber	1.53	77	900

Table 4: Constituent properties for the autophagous structure-fuel struts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 shows the multifunctional performance for the PLI laminates in bending. The stiffness and strength are greatest for the carbon-epoxy, followed by the carbon-weave, and then the non-reinforced laminate. The stored energy follows an opposite trend. The highest specific energy occurs in the non-reinforced laminate, followed by the carbon-weave and carbon-epoxy reinforced laminates, respectively. The stiffness index changes only slightly as the number of PLI layers increases, decreasing for the carbon-epoxy reinforced laminates, staying the same for the carbon-weave, and actually increasing

for the plain packaged PLI configurations. The strength index decreases significantly for the reinforced materials and hardly at all for packaged PLI as the number of PLI layers increases. The strength index corresponds to the constituent that yields first. In all of the above cases, yielding occurs first in the Dai-Nippon packaging. A small amount of package yielding is okay, just so long as long as the aluminum barrier-layer and sealed edges remain intact. Yielding of the PLI bicell by normal stresses due to bending or a shear stresses due to transverse loading, would likely lead to electrical failure.

The PLI and packaging thickness' and their mechanical properties are fixed. The number of PLI layers is free. In most applications, the number of required PLI layers will be governed by the system's energy requirements. That leaves the reinforcement layer composition (i.e., mechanical properties) and thickness as the free design variables. In the present case, the thickness' of the carbon-epoxy and carbon-weave reinforcement layers can vary. One might ask, are there optimal reinforcement thickness'? With regard to stiffness, the stiffness index for the reinforcement materials is much larger than that of the packaging and PLI. This means that the "optimum" configuration with respect to stiffness is that which maximizes the thickness of reinforcement.

For strength, the situation is more complicated because the composite's performance is based on the material that yields first. The largest strains occur at the outer fibers in bending. Carbon-epoxy is the outermost material in one of the above configurations; packaging is the outermost material in the other two configurations. In the above configurations with minimal reinforcement, yielding always occurs first in the packaging. Increasing the carbon-fiber weave thickness, which is inside of the packaging, strengthens the laminate but also pushes the packaging further out from the neutral axis, which increases normal strain it is exposed to during bending. Hence, yielding will always occur first in the packaging in this configuration. Increasing the carbon-epoxy thickness does eventually lead to a shift in first yield from the packaging to the carbon-epoxy layer. This is shown by the kink in the blue-dashed strength curve for carbon-epoxy in Figure 8 at a thickness of 0.36 mm and specific energy of 95.2 Wh/kg. The carbon-epoxy and the packaging yield at the same time at this thickness. This configuration is optimal in the sense that both the carbon-epoxy and packaging are fully utilized in their strength capabilities.

Consider the multifunctional performance of the reinforced laminates at the specific energy value of 95.2 Wh/kg. The carbon-epoxy configuration is optimal at this point, under load-limitations, with a thickness of 0.36 mm. The corresponding thickness of the carbon-fiber weave is 0.71 mm. The corresponding performance index values are listed below in Table 5:

Configuration	Reinforcement Thickness, mm	Total Thickness, mm	Strength Index	Stiffness Index
Carbon-epoxy reinforced	0.36	11.7	11.6	17.7
Carbon-fiber weave reinforced	0.71	18.7	7.3	25.5

Table 5: Total thickness and performance index values for configurations with specific energy of 95.2 Wh/kg.

If strength is the design constraint, then the ratio of the carbon-epoxy to carbon-weave configuration mass is $7.3/11.6=0.63$, and if stiffness is the constraint, then the ratio of the carbon-weave to carbon-epoxy configuration mass is $17.7/25.5=0.69$. In other words, the carbon-epoxy component will be 37% lighter than the carbon-weave component in a strength-limited design, and the carbon-weave component will be 31% lighter than the carbon-epoxy component in a deflection-limited design. These weight savings translate directly into endurance time increases of 56% and 47%, respectively, using the 1.5 weight factor from Eq. (2). This is a significant increase in performance that would be available from the proper selection of materials and architecture in the structure-battery laminate.

Figure 10 shows the axial stiffness index versus stored specific energy for the autophagous struts. Several configurations are considered all of which have a fixed outer diameter of 2.5 cm. Points on the ordinate correspond to tubes with no internal structure-fuel material (i.e., zero specific energy), and points furthest to the right correspond to tubes of pure structure-fuel. In-between these two limits are composite autophagous tubes with varying amounts of structure-fuel material.

The Mg-Fe structure-fuel struts show two trends. The change in mechanical performance with increasing Mg-Fe is nil for the Ti-6Al-4V and 7075-T6 configurations and negative for the carbon-epoxy configuration. The slope of these curves is determined by the sign of the difference between the axial stiffness indices for pure structure-fuel versus pure structure (i.e., $E_{S-F}/\rho_{S-F} - E_S/\rho_S$). The performance of the composite autophagous strut should improve or decline as the outer tube structure material is replaced with structure-fuel material having a higher or lower performance index value. This is confirmed with the carbon-polymer struts, which show improvement in mechanical performance as higher-performing structure-fuel is added. The curves in Figure 10 provide useful design information. Assume that specific energy for the autophagous struts is a select design requirement. For specific energy requirements above ~ 9 kJ/g, we should specify the polymer structure-fuel with an aluminum or titanium outer tube. If the requirement is less than ~ 9 kJ/g, then supercorroding alloy in a carbon-epoxy tube is a better choice. Of course, each of the autophagous strut concepts has auxiliary energy transformation equipment associated with them that must be taken into account in the design process.

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FIGURES

Figure 1: Prismatic composite beam with internal loads applied at the ends.

Figure 2: Composite cross-section created from assorted rectangular material regions.

Figure 3: Ragone data for several common electrical energy storage materials. Discharge times are shown as red lines on the plot.

Figure 4: Plastic-lithium-ion bicell. PVDF-HFP polymer “glue” (~25% by weight) holds the active particles and layers stacked together.

Figure 5: Dai-Nippon EP-40 packaging. The nylon can be molded, the aluminum keeps the electrolyte in and moisture out, and the polypropylene is the inner heat-sealing layer.

Figure 6: Structure-battery symmetric half-sections. One, two or eight layers of bicell with packaging and carbon-weave (SW) or carbon-epoxy (CE).

Figure 7: Multifunctional performance for bending of multi-layered structure-battery laminates. In the figure, CE: carbon-epoxy; #P: number of bicell layers; and SW: satin-weave carbon-fiber.

Figure 8: Multifunctional performance for the 8-ply PLI reinforced structure-battery laminates in bending as a function of reinforcement thickness. The change in slope of the carbon-epoxy strength curve at $t \sim 0.36$ mm (CE) corresponds to a change in the material of first yield from the packaging to the carbon-epoxy outer layer.

Figure 9: Annular configuration for the autophagous structure-fuel struts.

Figure 10: Performance indices for axial stiffness plotted against specific energy for the autophagous struts.